

Fast algorithms for identification of rapidly fading channels

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ABSTRACT

The problem of identification/tracking of rapidly fading communication channels is considered. When the channel coefficients vary rapidly with time the most frequently used weighted least squares (WLS) and least mean squares (LMS) algorithms are not capable of tracking the changes satisfactorily. To obtain good estimation results one has to use more specialized adaptive filters, such as the basis function (BF) algorithms which are based on explicit models of parameter changes. Unfortunately, estimators of this kind are numerically very demanding. The paper introduces a new class of recursive algorithms which combine low computational requirements, typical of WLS and LMS filters, with very good tracking capabilities, typical of BF filters.

1 Introduction

Identification/tracking of time-varying coefficients of a mobile communication channel allows one to perform channel equalization and hence to significantly reduce the negative effects of intersymbol interference. The signal $y(t)$ received by the mobile radio system can be written down in the form:

$$y(t) = \varphi^T(t)\theta(t) + v(t), \quad (1)$$

where $\varphi(t) = [u(t), \dots, u(t-n+1)]^T$ is the regression vector made up of transmitted (complex) symbols, $\theta(t) = [\theta_1(t), \dots, \theta_n(t)]^T$ denotes the vector of time-varying channel coefficients (characterizing the impulse response of the channel along with the transmitter and receiver filters) and $v(t)$ is an additive (white) noise.

When the multipath effects are caused by a few strong reflectors and when the path delays change linearly with time due to the receiver/transmitter motion, the communication channel (such as mobile radio channel or underwater acoustic channel) can be regarded as almost periodically time-varying. In cases like this, the time-varying impulse response of the channel $\{\theta_i(t), i = 1, \dots, n\}$ can be approximated by a weighted sum of complex exponentials $e^{j\omega_i t}$, $i = 1, \dots, k$ [3] where k is the number of dominant reflectors and ω_i denote the corresponding Doppler shifts.

Even though the angular frequencies ω_i are usually not known *a priori* they can be easily estimated in the startup phase of equalization [3]. Consequently, in the case considered channel parameters can be approximated as linear combinations of *known* functions of time.

2 Weighted basis function estimators

The method of basis functions is based on an explicit model of parameter variation. It is assumed that the parameter trajectory can be approximated by a linear combination of known functions of time called the basis functions. Since in practice the coefficients of such functional series expansions can't be regarded as constant in the entire time domain, the estimation incorporates the elements of data weighting. The weighting sequence $\{w(i)\}$ which obeys

$$w(0) \geq w(1) \geq \dots \geq 0, \quad \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} w(i) < \infty, \quad (2)$$

makes the estimates more dependent on the recently collected data points and less dependent on the data points collected in the remote past. Owing to this finite-memory property the weighted basis function (WBF) estimators are capable of tracking slow variations in the expansion coefficients which makes identification procedures more robust.

Denote by $T_t = [1, \dots, t]$ the expanding analysis window and by $\{f_1(s), \dots, f_k(s), s \in T_t\}$ the basis set. We will assume that the basis functions are linearly independent on T_t . Depending on the adopted model of parameter evolution the WBF estimators can be defined in two different ways [1].

The running basis WBF estimators correspond to the *forward-time* description of parameter changes

$$\theta_i(s) = \sum_{j=1}^k a_{ij} f_j(s), \quad s \in T_t, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

whereas the fixed basis WBF estimators rest on the *backward-time* description

$$\theta_i(t-s+1) = \sum_{j=1}^k b_{ij} f_j(s), \quad s \in T_t, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

As long as local approximation is concerned the reverse-time model (4) is not less justified than the forward-time model (3); as a matter of fact it better fits the truncated functional series expansion argument often used when introducing the basis function approach.

Since in general the subspace $\mathcal{F}_t^+$ spanned by $\{f_1(s), \dots, f_k(s), s \in T_t\}$ differs from the subspace $\mathcal{F}_t^-$ spanned by $\{f_1(t-s+1), \dots, f_k(t-s+1), s \in T_t\}$, the running basis estimators differ from the fixed basis estimators. Both estimation algorithms yield identical results if the basis is direction invariant [1], i.e. if for $f(t) = [f_1(t), \dots, f_k(t)]^T$ and for every $t > k$ one can find a nonsingular $k \times k$ matrix $D(t)$ such that it holds

$$f(t-s+1) = D(t)f(s), \quad \forall s \in T_t \quad (5)$$

2.1 Running basis estimator

Running basis WBF estimators are based on the forward-time model (3). The term ‘running basis’ refers to the fact that as the time runs from say t_1 to t_2 , the basis functions are simply extended to cover the additional time interval $(t_1, t_2 >)$.

To facilitate further analysis we will introduce a Kronecker product $A \otimes B$ [$im \times jn$] of two matrices A [$i \times j$] and B [$m \times n$]:

$$A \otimes B \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}B & \dots & a_{1j}B \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ a_{i1}B & \dots & a_{ij}B \end{bmatrix}.$$

Denote by $\alpha = [a_{11}, \dots, a_{1k}, \dots, a_{n1}, \dots, a_{nk}]^T$ the vector of coefficients in (3) and by

$$\psi(s) = [u(s)f^T(t), \dots, u(s-n+1)f^T(t)]^T = \varphi(s) \otimes f(s)$$

the generalized regression vector. Using this shorthand notation one can rewrite the system equation (1) in the form

$$y(s) = \psi^T(s)\alpha + v(s), \quad s \in T_t \quad (6)$$

Formally α is written down as a constant vector but its components, the expansion coefficients a_{ij} , are often slowly time-varying. It is known that the method of weighted least squares is capable of tracking such slow time variations. Using the method of weighted least squares one arrives at the following ‘localized’ estimate of α :

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\alpha}(t) &= \arg \min_{\alpha} \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} w(i) |y(t-i) - \psi^T(t-i)\alpha|^2 \\ &= (R_+^*(t))^{-1} s_+(t). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} R_+(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} w(i) \psi(t-i) \psi^\dagger(t-i), \\ s_+(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} w(i) y(t-i) \psi^*(t-i) \end{aligned}$$

(A^* denotes a complex conjugate of a matrix A and $A^\dagger$ stands for its complex conjugate-transpose).

After combining (7) with (3) the running basis WBF estimator of a time-varying vector of system parameters $\theta(t)$ can be expressed in the following form:

$$\hat{\theta}_+(t) = H(t)\hat{\alpha}(t), \quad (8)$$

where $H(t) = I_n \otimes f^T(t)$.

2.2 Fixed basis estimators

Suppose that the backward-time model (4) of parameter changes is adopted. Note that in this case the basis set $\{f_1(t-s+1), \dots, f_k(t-s+1), s \in T_t\}$ is redefined for each new value of t . If (4) holds the system equation (1) can be written down in the form

$$y(s) = \psi_0^T(t, s)\beta + v(s), \quad s \in T_t \quad (9)$$

where $\beta = [b_{11}, \dots, b_{1k}, \dots, b_{n1}, \dots, b_{nk}]^T$ is the vector of coefficients in (4) and

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_0(t, s) &= [u(s)f^T(t-s+1), \dots, u(s-n+1)f^T(t-s+1)]^T \\ &= \varphi(s) \otimes f(t-s+1) \end{aligned}$$

denotes the corresponding generalized regression vector. The weighted least squares estimator of β can be obtained in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\beta}(t) &= \arg \min_{\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} w(i) |y(t-i) - \psi_0^T(t, t-i)\beta|^2 \\ &= (R_-^*(t))^{-1} s_-(t). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} R_-(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} w(i) \psi_0(t, t-i) \psi_0^\dagger(t, t-i), \\ s_-(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} w(i) y(t-i) \psi_0^*(t, t-i). \end{aligned}$$

Based on (10) the fixed basis WBF estimator can be expressed in the form

$$\hat{\theta}_-(t) = H_0(t, t)\hat{\beta}(t), \quad (11)$$

where $H_0(t, s) = I_n \otimes f^T(t-s+1)$.

3 Recursive weighted basis function estimators

From practical viewpoint it is important to find such basis and weighting sequences which make the corresponding WBF estimators recursively computable. Recursive computability of $\hat{\theta}_+(t)$ and $\hat{\theta}_-(t)$ can be guaranteed if two conditions are met. First, the basis functions should be recursively computable, i.e. there should exist a $k \times k$ nonsingular matrix A such that it holds

$$f(s+1) = Af(s), \quad \forall s > 0 \quad (12)$$

Second, the weighting sequence should also be recursively computable. Note that the first condition is satisfied for the basis set consisting of complex exponentials recommended for mobile radio applications; the matrix A in (12) takes in this case the form $A = \text{diag}\{e^{j\omega_1}, \dots, e^{j\omega_k}\}$.

To satisfy the second condition we will use the exponentially decaying weighting sequence $w(i) = \lambda^i$, $0 < \lambda < 1$ which corresponds to the so-called exponential forgetting technique widely used in system identification. Under the conditions stated above it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} R_+(t) &= \lambda R_+(t-1) + \psi(t)\psi^\dagger(t), \\ s_+(t) &= \lambda s_+(t-1) + y(t)\psi^*(t). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Similarly, since $\psi_0(t, s) = A_n \psi_0(t-1, s)$, $1 \leq s < t$, where $A_n = I_n \otimes A$, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} R_-(t) &= \lambda A_n R_-(t-1) A_n^\dagger + \psi_0(t, t)\psi_0^\dagger(t, t), \\ s_-(t) &= \lambda A_n^* s_-(t-1) + y(t)\psi_0^*(t, t). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Applying the well-known matrix inversion lemma to (13) one arrives at the following algorithm for recursive computation of the running basis estimator

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\alpha}(t) &= \hat{\alpha}(t-1) + K_+^*(t)\epsilon(t), \\ \epsilon(t) &= y(t) - \psi^T(t)\hat{\alpha}(t-1), \\ K_+(t) &= \frac{P_+(t-1)\psi(t)}{\lambda + \psi^\dagger(t)P_+(t-1)\psi(t)}, \\ P_+(t) &= \frac{1}{\lambda} (P_+(t-1) - K_+(t)\psi^\dagger(t)P_+(t-1)). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Similar calculations carried out for the fixed basis estimator yield

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\beta}(t) &= C_n^T [\hat{\beta}(t-1) + K_-^*(t)\epsilon(t)], \\ \epsilon(t) &= y(t) - \zeta^T(t)\hat{\beta}(t-1), \\ K_-(t) &= \frac{P_-(t-1)\zeta(t)}{\lambda + \zeta^\dagger(t)P_-(t-1)\zeta(t)}, \\ P_-(t) &= \frac{1}{\lambda} C_n^\dagger [P_-(t-1) - K_-(t)\zeta^\dagger(t)P_-(t-1)] C_n \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\zeta(t) = \varphi(t) \otimes f(0)$ and $C_n = A_n^{-1}$. Note that for the exponential basis $f(0) = [1, \dots, 1]^T$ which simplifies the algorithm.

The fixed basis algorithm is more complex than the running basis algorithm since it requires performing three additional matrix multiplications involving the matrix C_n . Note, however, that for a basis consisting of complex exponentials it holds $A^{-1} = A^* = \text{diag}\{e^{-j\omega_1}, \dots, e^{-j\omega_k}\}$ and therefore the matrix $C_n = I_n \otimes A^*$ is diagonal. The amount of additional computations is in this case insignificant. We will show in the next section that when the regression matrices in (7) or (10) are replaced by their approximations, the fixed basis framework lends itself to more efficient computational algorithms than the running basis framework.

Remark

The basis consisting of complex exponentials is not direction invariant and therefore $\hat{\theta}_+(t) \neq \hat{\theta}_-(t)$. Note, however, that for $f(s) = [e^{j\omega_1 s}, \dots, e^{j\omega_k s}]^T$ the following modified version of condition (5) is satisfied

$$f(t-s+1) = D(t)f^*(s), \quad \forall s \in T_t \quad (17)$$

with $D(t) = \text{diag}\{e^{j\omega_1(t+1)}, \dots, e^{j\omega_k(t+1)}\}$.

Using (17) it is straightforward to show that the fixed basis algorithm corresponding to the conjugate basis set $\{e^{-j\omega_1 s}, \dots, e^{-j\omega_k s}\}$ yields identical results as the running basis algorithm corresponding to the set $\{e^{j\omega_1 s}, \dots, e^{j\omega_k s}\}$.

4 Fast modified WBF algorithms

Even for moderate values of n (the number of channel coefficients) and k (the number of basis functions) the WBF algorithms are computationally very demanding as they require updating the $nk \times nk$ covariance matrices $P_+(t)$ and $P_-(t)$. The low complexity stochastic gradient counterpart of (15) can be obtained [3] by replacing the matrix $P_+(t)$ with the scalar stepsize $\mu > 0$

$$\hat{\alpha}(t) = \hat{\alpha}(t-1) + \mu \psi^*(t)\epsilon(t). \quad (18)$$

Despite its simplicity the LMS-based algorithm (18) has similar parameter tracking capabilities as the WLS-based algorithm (15) - see [4]. Unfortunately, it may suffer from a very slow initial convergence.

Suppose that the sequence of regression vectors $\{\varphi(t)\}$ is a covariance stationary ergodic process with *known* positive definite covariance matrix $\text{cov}[\varphi(t)] = \Phi_o > 0$. Note that in mobile radio applications where $\varphi(t)$ is made up of uncorrelated random variables (input symbols) it holds $\Phi_o = \sigma_u^2 I_n$ where $\sigma_u^2 = E[|u(t)|^2]$.

It is straightforward to show that when λ tends to 1 the regression matrices $R_+(t)$ and $R_-(t)$ tend, in the mean square sense, to their expectations

$$E[R_+(t)] = \Phi_o \otimes F_+(t), \quad E[R_-(t)] = \Phi_o \otimes F_-(t),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F_+(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} \lambda^i f(t-i)f^\dagger(t-i), \\ F_-(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} \lambda^i f(i+1)f^\dagger(i+1). \end{aligned}$$

Let $G_+(t) = F_+^{-1}(t)$, $G_-(t) = F_-^{-1}(t)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_+(t) &= (E[R_+(t)])^{-1} = \Phi_o^{-1} \otimes G_+(t), \\ \Pi_-(t) &= (E[R_-(t)])^{-1} = \Phi_o^{-1} \otimes G_-(t). \end{aligned}$$

Replacing the regression matrices in (7) and (10) with their expectations one obtains the following simplified WBF algorithms

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\alpha}(t) &= \hat{\alpha}(t-1) + \Pi_+^*(t)\psi^*(t)\epsilon(t), \\ \epsilon(t) &= y(t) - \psi^T(t)\hat{\alpha}(t-1) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\beta}(t) &= C_n^T [\hat{\beta}(t-1) + \Pi_-^*(t)\zeta^*(t)\epsilon(t)], \\ \epsilon(t) &= y(t) - \zeta^T(t)\hat{\beta}(t-1) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The matrices $G_+(t)$ and $G_-(t)$ needed to compute the gain matrices $\Pi_+(t)$ and $\Pi_-(t)$ can be evaluated recursively using

$$L_+(t) = \frac{G_+(t-1)f(t)}{\lambda + f^\dagger(t)G_+(t-1)f(t)}, \quad (21)$$

$$G_+(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda} [G_+(t-1) - L_+(t)f^\dagger(t)G_+(t-1)],$$

and

$$L_-(t) = \frac{G_-(t-1)f(0)}{\lambda + f^\dagger(0)G_-(t-1)f(0)}, \quad (22)$$

$$G_-(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda} C^\dagger [G_-(t-1) - L_-(t)f^\dagger(0)G_-(t-1)] C$$

where $C = A^{-1}$.

Using the identity $(A \otimes B)(C \otimes D)$, which holds for Kronecker products, one arrives at relationships

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_+(t)\psi(t) &= (\Phi_o^{-1}\varphi(t)) \otimes L_+(t), \\ \Pi_-(t)\zeta(t) &= (\Phi_o^{-1}\varphi(t)) \otimes L_-(t), \end{aligned}$$

In mobile radio applications it holds that $\Phi_o^{-1}\varphi(t) = (1/\sigma_u^2)\varphi(t)$ which further simplifies (19) and (20).

The modified WBF algorithms have clear computational advantages over the original algorithms as they require updating the $k \times k$ dimensional matrices $G_+(t)$ and $G_-(t)$ instead of the $kn \times kn$ dimensional matrices $P_+(t)$ and $P_-(t)$. Interestingly, despite the simplifications introduced the tracking capabilities of algorithms (19) and (20) are approximately the same [4] as tracking capabilities of algorithms (15) and (16), respectively.

The computational complexity of modified algorithms is greater than complexity of the gradient algorithm (18) but they guarantee fast initial convergence typical of WLS filters.

The modified fixed basis WBF algorithm has an important computational advantage over its running basis counterpart. It is straightforward to show that as time goes to infinity the quantities $F_-(t)$ and $L_-(t)$ approach their *constant* steady state values $F_-(\infty)$ and $L_-(\infty)$. Hence when the initial convergence period is over one can stop updating the gain vector $L_-(t)$. The running basis algorithm does not have this property. Note that when the gain vector is ‘frozen’ the computational complexity of the modified WBF algorithm is comparable with complexity of the gradient algorithm!

5 Computer simulations

The test case involved a periodically time varying channel ($n = 2$) with coefficients given as combinations of three basis functions ($k = 3$, a direct path plus two reflectors): $f_1(s) = 1$, $f_2(s) = e^{j(2\pi/T_2)s}$, $f_3(s) = e^{j(2\pi/T_3)s}$ with T_2 and T_3 equal to 120 and 200 samples, respectively. These numbers are close to real conditions met for a carrier frequency of 900 MHz, a bit rate around 20 kbit/s and a vehicle moving at 100 km/h. The 4-QAM input signals were generated ($u(t) = \pm 1 \pm j$,

Figure 1: Comparison of mean square parameter estimation errors for three estimation algorithms: WBF (thin line), modified WBF (thick line) and gradient (dotted line).

$\sigma_u^2 = 2$) and the noise variance was set to $\sigma_v^2 = 0.4373$, which corresponds to the average SNR of 15 dB.

Figure 1 shows evolution of the mean square parameter estimation errors (averaged over 200 simulation runs) obtained for the original fixed basis WBF algorithm (16), the modified fixed basis WBF algorithm (20) and the gradient algorithm (18). The forgetting constant λ was set to 0.99 which corresponds to an equivalent estimation memory of approximately 58 samples (see [2] and [4] for more details on determination of the estimation memory for WBF filters). The stepsize for the gradient algorithm was set to $\mu = 0.00572$; for such value of μ the steady state misadjustment of the gradient algorithm is identical as misadjustment of the WBF algorithm, i.e. all filters have the same memory. The plots clearly show advantages of the proposed estimation schemes.

References

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